

Academic Problems Faced by Today Head Teachers in Achieving Educational Roadmap

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Abstract

Education plays a pivotal role to reform a nation or society for the betterment of human life while educational institutes and teachers play a central role. The main aim of the study was to identify the academic problems faced by the heads of public secondary schools in achieving CM roadmap. The study was descriptive in nature — the population of the study comprised of 456 secondary schools of Sahiwal division. The sample of the study consisted of 150 schools, 50 schools from each district of Sahiwal division. A Self developed questionnaire was used as a research instrument. The academic problems faced by today head teacher related to students such as; health, A.V. aids in their classrooms, low enrollment, drop out, domestic issue, attitudinal issues, uniform, and safety problem while the school problems such as teaching and non teaching staff according to requirement, drinking water, toilets as per students strength, electricity, classrooms as per students strength and the problem of academic support facilities. The problems related to quality education like as; low STR, low STR as per subject, learning material, a tablet for LND test, LND booklets, teacher guides for lesson planning and the problem of preparation of low-cost, no-cost material.

Keywords: Academic Problems, CM Roadmap, Head Teachers, Students, Public Schools, Quality Education.

Introduction

In Pakistan, the policy setters have hardly been acknowledged the value of education and so much of idealistic and least practical initiatives have been taken in the form of allocation of public budget. Education is a fundamental human right so it must be accepted as a major priority for the nation. It is justifiable that no society can be civilized if a large part of its population is uneducated. Education equips humans with a key to lift up the level of their lifestyle and shatters down obstacles of so called classes. It lays the foundation for mental development and comprehension of a challenging life. Education is a key to progress in all walks of life. Education system comprises a number of significant human resources in which teachers take up a central role among other resources. The teaching staff is a vital force in the development of education. The behavior, expertise, and knowledge of teaching staff justify the system of education as a whole (Hussain, 2015).

Punjab in Pakistan is the largest populous province that has undergone numerous initiatives for education development to achieve educational goals. On the other hand, about 25 % of school going children is still away from school either due to the reason they were never enrolled or due to the reason they were dropped out in the beginning. Low promotion rates to secondary level need keen attention. Further, current observations have explored that knowledge and comprehension of the students in major subjects are terribly weak. On the other hand improvement of students' learning in schools is another critical problem — these models for improvement point out the importance of valuable factors in the schools, meaning that a good quality school might be exemplary for social and cultural differences (Abdullah et al., 2017).

A roadmap is a strategic plan that defines a goal or desired outcome and includes the major steps or milestones needed to reach it. The Punjab Schools Reform Roadmap was initiated in 2010 by Mian Muhammad Shahbaz Sharif, the Chief Minister of Punjab. The Chief Ministers' Roadmap for schools was started in 2010. It was funded by DFID. It was planned principally to accelerate the process of educational outcomes. It was launched in Punjab under PESRP. The administrative structure of the organization aimed at to achieve the targets at schools and districts level and to send the results to the chief minister of Punjab. After the implementation of this program, monitoring teams started visiting schools monthly actively and

consistently. These improved visits teacher and student attendance enhanced enrollment and decreased students' dropout hopefully (Barber, 2013).

By launching this program, the government provided new teachers to the schools, collected data based on the feedback of the roadmap, removed missing facilities in the schools, granted stipends and scholarships to the students, ensured free textbooks and awarded ranking to the schools and districts on quarter basis. In this way, this is a convincing model that moved up speedily and made it an easy access to the right to education for all. In spite of these good measures, there are some critical questions about the program that cannot be responded presently. (World Economic Forum's Global Agenda Council on Pakistan, 2012-2014).

In a nutshell, education plays a leading role in the uplifting economic and social standard of the people in the country. Quality of education is the most important factor, which helps the youth to raise the flag of the country high up to the sky. In Pakistan, since coming into existence until now, education sector in Pakistan with reference to Punjab province faces a lot of problems needs to be solved in due course of time. Similarly, Government of Punjab is trying its best to improve the quality of education by launching various programs to improve quality education in schools. Chief Minister's Roadmap is another effort to develop the quality of education within the province which is under implementation process. The objectives of the plan are expected to be achieved in the near future in due course of time.

It is a fact that from the inception of Pakistan till now more than dozen national education policies and plans, various national educational conferences/seminars have been conducted in Pakistan but the required objectives for improving quality of education within the country including Punjab province, have not been achieved due to many reasons. There are many factors responsible for the low quality of education in the country including Punjab province, so the researcher decided to conduct a research study on "Academic Problems Faced by Today Head Teachers in Achieving Educational Roadmap."

Objectives of the Study

1. To highlight the academic problems related to students regarding Chief Minister's Roadmap by public secondary school heads.
2. To explore the academic problems related to schools regarding Chief Minister's Roadmap by public secondary school heads.
3. To identify the problems related to Quality Education regarding Chief Minister's Roadmap faced by the public secondary school heads.

Research Questions

1. What are the academic problems related to students regarding Chief Minister's Roadmap faced by public secondary school heads?
2. What are the academic problems related to schools regarding Chief Minister's Roadmap faced by public secondary school heads?
3. What are the problems related to quality education regarding Chief Minister's Roadmap faced by the public secondary school heads?

The significance of the Study

Quality of education is the main factor for uplifting education standard of the country. This can only be achieved by the provision of instructional and physical facilities to the institutions along with updated professional training to teaching force and their respective school heads. This study is significant to the educational policy makers, planners, administrative authorities, decision makers and various agencies involved for improving quality of education in Pakistan with reference to Punjab Province to suggest measures for overcoming problems creating hindrances for the uplifting quality of education at secondary level in the province. The study will be helpful to school heads at the secondary level to take necessary steps at their disposal for improving quality of education in their respective educational institutions. This study is

also helpful for teaching force at all levels especially at the secondary level for making necessary improvements in their methods of teaching and classroom management.

Research Methodology

The researcher used the quantitative research method that was descriptive in nature, so the researcher used the survey method for data collection — the population of the study comprised of all (456) male and female public secondary school head teachers of Sahiwal Division (Pakpattan, Okara and Sahiwal districts). The sample of the study was selected at a rate of 33 % of the target population (Gay, 2012). The 150 male and female public secondary school head teachers were selected as a sample through simple random sampling technique. The researcher used self-developed questionnaire was developed on 5 points likert scale to collect required information from the respondents.

Review of the Related Literature

The current amendment in the constitution of Pakistan played a historical role in the field of education. This 18th amendment made it possible to provide free education to the children of the age of 5 to 16 in Pakistan on a mandatory base. This step made it possible to achieve Millennium Development Goals especially regarding education in which Pakistan was far behind. This geared up the speed of achievement. But the problem to be considered is that sufficient time has passed, but no further legislation is made for its implementation. Further legislation is required by the Provincial Governments for the proper implementation of Article 25-A. It is clear that its implementation will require subsequent budget allocation that is a hurdle for this developing country (Malik, 2011).

The Government of Punjab has launched a number of education reform steps in order to develop education department. Though 25% of the school age children are still not reaching school either for the reason that they were not enrolled or because they were struck off due to any reason. Low promotion rates to secondary level are of great importance. Further, latest assessments have revealed that the level of students learning and understanding in basic subjects is sorrowfully weak. There are numerous learning problems in school. High performing schools invite more children from the backward area, for the reason the parents look forward to better outputs from education. In the way, the time and resources invested in learning become valuable (Habib, 2013).

Ahmad et al. (2013) stated that the condition of the education sector in developing countries is not hopeful and optimistic. Pakistan is also still in the list of progressing states. Low enrollment at primary level, huge differences among regions, lack of professional staff, insufficiency of teaching learning material and pitiable physical condition of an infrastructure of institutions point out the low performance of this department. Another most important reason behind the discouraging performance of the education system of Pakistan is a very low level of public investment. Public investment in the education sector was less than 2 %. Now in presently, it has been enhanced up to 2.2 %. There are some critical secondary school problems such as; budget allocation, leadership pressure, social acknowledgment, inadequate residence, uncertain transfers and deficiency of staff.

Islamabad Policy Research Institute (2015), found the educational problems in Pakistan of a type such as; inappropriate planning Pakistan is lagging behind in achieving national and international goals and commitments. There are some managerial and financial gaps making unable to achieve the required promises. It is essential to understand that apart from the government there are a number of social problems that cause hindrance in the provision of education. These issues are deeply rooted in social and cultural beliefs. Controlling the situation is such a hard job, and the challenge of universal primary education cannot be achieved until these issues are uprooted.

In this age of advancement, the infrastructure of an educational institution has been considered not only the set up of facilitation but also a source of inspiration and attraction for the students. The infrastructure of schools consists of the classrooms, electricity, fans, furniture, toilets and schools building, etc. These facilities can provide an institution a competitive, aesthetic and moral impact on the advantage. Availability of washrooms is considerable in fulfilling the basic facilities of school for students to provide

them with an easy atmosphere for peaceful learning. The motivation of students towards their learning may be influenced by poor classroom facilities, parents and others in the home (Hassan, Malik & Khan, 2013).

In this modern age, required quality of education can hardly be achieved without the availability of required facilities for teachers and students. A variety of teaching learning material, proper classrooms, toilets, boundary wall, furniture, drinking water and availability of electricity is required in a school for better learning. Electric water pump, electrical fans, computers, security cameras, electric water coolers and bulbs for light are being operated by electricity. So electricity is a must in the schools to fulfill electrical needs. It has exactly been said that learning atmosphere works as a third teacher. The conducive learning environment is created by providing the required facilities that not only facilitates the students and teachers but also creates interest in the process of teaching and learning (Saeed & Wain, 2011).

Classroom management plays a vital role in effective and long-term teaching. Successful classroom management starts with well-prepared and proficient lesson planning preparation and supports the teacher to teach in a good manner and students to learn in a better way. Students' performance enhances in a conducive classroom environment and an atmosphere where they feel secure, safe, cared for and active. Keeping in view the situation of students the best classroom provides the students with opportunities of socialization and interesting learning. For teachers, good classroom management creates protective discipline and attractive learning. To ensure constructive classroom management, it should be well prepared and assisted. The physical display of classroom gives students with helpful education and develops easy teaching learning practice. Physical facilities prove supportive in making the school better as a whole. Physical classroom environment consists of different items such as light, temperature, ventilation, size, floor, walls, charts, furniture, carpets, whiteboards, computers, etc. Teacher and students are the main and live part of the classroom (Suleman, 2014).

So far as the school facilities are concerned, the surroundings where the students learn are very contributive, and the lack of proper environment causes improper learning. Learning environment has rightly been called the third teacher, but it should be kept in mind that the environment is not an end in itself; the settings should be overviewed continuously. Space plays a significant role in creating an attractive environment for learning. The environment should be full of learning resources making it possible to provide the students a wide scope to develop their interests and to practice and apply their learning. In this way, they make their own learning. The classroom should be on easy access where it can be easily supervised. It should also be with attached washroom (Saeed & Wain, 2011).

Student absenteeism is a global problem, but in Pakistan, it has reached a critical level in spite of the care and pursues the government is investing in solving out the problem. On 15th of August, 2016 when schools were re-opened after summer vacation, electronic media was criticizing the absenteeism of the students. Almost 80-90% students were not willing to go to their schools even after enjoying a long summer vacation. The reason may be terrorism, child kidnapping, poor economic condition or any other reason but one thing is obvious that mass of the students is absent from school for one reason or the other (Chaudary et al. 2017).

Farooq et al. (2011) found that students' performance is treated as a top priority for teachers to achieve a quality education. The variables include learning activities inside and outside of the school that influence students' quality of academic outcomes. These factors may be named as learners' factors, parental factors, school factors, social factors, and peer factors.

In actual classroom circumstances, teachers confront a number of students' behavior problems. The behavior problems urge to move away from certain pre-set rules and regulations of the institution. The different behavior problems in the classroom can be consisted on fellows-bullying, quarreling, joking, stealing, absenteeism, disobedience and insubordination, lying, deceitful, unpunctuality, impoliteness, destructiveness, drug or alcohol Addiction (Tiwari & Panwar, 2014).

Memon (2007) is of the view that Teachers are possibly central part of any education system. It is also assumed that teachers start their job without necessary skills and teaching methodology. Even after joining their job as a carrier, teachers hardly show their concern for the jobs and consider that once they have got a job of teaching, now they are teachers forever. This type of professional attitude causes hurdle in

the way of professional development. The quality of teachers influences both the quality of institutions and the learning of students.

The chief minister declared a comprehensive message for the roadmap remarking it corner-stone of the policy and quality education as the topmost priority of the Government of Punjab with initiatives undertaken for teachers, students, and school infrastructure. The key components of the Chief Minister's School Reforms Road Map are: steps taken for teachers, steps for students, steps for schools, 100% enrollment, 100% retention, performance based positions of districts, achievement of quality education, governance, actions for assistance, transparent transfer policy and indicators for ranking of district (Chief Minister's School Reforms Road Map, 2010).

Presentation and Analysis of the Results

Table: 1 Academic Problem Related to Students

Sr. No	Academic Problems Related to Students	Percentages					Mean	SD
		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA		
1.	Head teacher faces problems due to students illness	22	53	10	6	8.69	3.74	1.13
2.	Lack of A.V. aids creates problems for the head teacher	11.30	56.70	7.29	22.69	2	3.52	1.028
3.	Enrollment of students creates problems for head teacher	44	38	9.30	6.70	2	4.15	0.98
4.	Students drop out has a challenge for head teacher	72	22.69	3.29	1.3	7	4.63	0.67
5.	Students' domestic problems create administrative hurdle for head teacher	33.10	50.70	7.29	6.70	7	4.16	1.022
6.	Head teacher faces administrative problems due to students' daily attendance	40	44.70	5.298	8	2	4.12	0.97
7.	Students' result affect head teachers' efficiency	30.69	52.70	7.29	4.70	4.70	4	0.997
8.	Students' attitude causes problems for head teacher	25.30	53.29	4.70	12.69	4	3.83	1.071
9.	Students' dress code is a problem for head teacher	14.69	42.70	10	27.30	5.29	3.31	1.181
10.	Head teacher faces students' safety problems	20.69	52	8.69	16.69	2	3.73	1.036

The data of table 1 shows that (75%) head teachers of public secondary schools show agreement that head teachers face problems due to students' illness and 68% head teachers show agreement with the statement that lack of A.V. aids creates problems for head teachers. The analysis of the data showed that 82% head teachers show agreement with the statement that enrollment of students creates problems for head teachers and 94.70% head teachers show agreement with the statement that students' drop out has a challenge for head teachers.

The table 1 shows that 83.80% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that students' domestic problems create administrative hurdles for head teachers. The results reflect that 84.70% head teachers show agreement with the statement that head teachers face administrative problems due to students' daily attendance while 83.40% head teachers show agreement with the statement that students' result affect head teachers' efficiency. It was found that 78.59% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that students' attitude causes problems for the head teacher. The data of the study revealed that 57.47% head teachers show agreement with the statement that students' dress code is a problem for head teachers whereas 72.70% head teachers show agreement with the statement that head teachers face students' safety problems.

Table 2: Academic Problems Related to School

Sr. No	Academic Problems Related to School	Percentages					Mean	SD
		SDA	DA	UD	A	SA		
1.	Teaching and supporting staff is available	18.69	55.29	6	18	2	3.71	1.03
2.	Drinking water is available in the school	32.70	62	2.702	2	7	4.24	0.66
3.	Washrooms are available as per students' strength	28.69	56.70	8	5.29	1.3	4.056	0.83
4.	Washrooms are functional in the school	39.29	58.70	7	7	7	4.34	0.60
5.	Electricity connection is available in the school	42.70	56.70	0	0	7	4.41	0.56
6.	Electricity is functional in classrooms	0	38.70	56.70	2	2.70	4.29	0.754
7.	Classrooms are available for all classes	28	38	2.70	13.30	17.30	3.47	1.464
8.	Classrooms are equipped with required facilities	22.69	42.70	2.70	23.30	8.69	3.47	1.304
9.	Government provides sufficient funds	18	56	6.70	15.30	4	3.689	1.06
10.	School has boundary wall	38.70	48	7.29	4	2	4.16	0.88

The table 2 indicated that 72% head teachers' shows agreement with the statement that teaching and supporting staff is available while 94.70% head teachers show agreement with the statement that drinking water is available in the school. The data shows that 85.40% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that washrooms are available as per students' strength. The study revealed that 98% of head teachers of public secondary schools show agreement with the statement that washrooms are functional in the school. The 99.40% head teachers show agreement with the statement that electrical connection is available in the school whereas 38.40% head teachers show agreement with the statement that electricity is functional in classrooms. The results of the study showed that 66% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that classrooms are available for all classes. The data from table 2 shows that 65.40% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that classrooms are equipped with required facilities. The study found that 74% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that the Government provides sufficient funds. It was found from the results of the study that 86.70% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that school has a boundary wall.

Table 3: Academic Problems Related to Quality Education

Sr. No	Academic Problems Related to Quality Education	Percentages					Mean	SD
		SDA	DA	UD	A	SA		
1.	Teaching staff is available as per STR	29.30	37.29	4	19.30	10	3.56	1.353
2.	Teaching staff is available as per subject	3.18	26.69	6.70	29.30	18	3	1.43
3.	Textbooks are available for students	7.40	53.29	1.3	2	2.70	4.26	0.81
4.	Learning material is available for students	28	50	8	12.699	1.3	3.91	0.99
5.	Tablet is available for LND	48.70	44.70	3.29	2	1.3	4.37	0.76
6.	Students have latest version of LND booklets	48	42	4	5.29	7	4.306	0.83
7.	Teachers seek training for LND	26.69	46.70	6.70	12.69	3.70	3.73	1.19
8.	Teacher guides are available for the teachers	41.29	49.29	5.29	2	2	4.25	0.81
9.	Teachers use teacher guides for lesson planning	18.69	54	7.29	16.69	3.29	3.68	1.06
10.	Teachers prepare low-cost, no-cost material for teaching	17.30	42	11.30	27.30	2	3.45	1.127

The table 3 reflects that 66.59% head teachers' shows agreement with the statement that teaching staff is available as per STR (student teacher ratio) and 29.86% head teachers show agreement with the statement that teaching staff is available as per subject. The results showed that 60.69% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that textbooks are available for students. The data revealed that 78% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that learning material is available for students. The 93.40% head teachers show agreement with the statement that the tab is available for LND.

The analysis reflects that 90% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that students have the latest version of LND booklets and 73.40% head teachers show agreement with the statement that teachers seek training for LND. It was observed that 90.59% of head teachers show agreement with the

statement that teacher guides are available for the teachers. The 72.70% head teachers show agreement with the statement that teachers use teacher guides for lesson planning. Table 3 indicated that 59.29% of head teachers show agreement with the statement that teachers seek training for LND.

Conclusions

In a nutshell, C.M. Roadmap is a quantitative mechanism to expedite the delivery of educational results in the shape of student's increasing enrollment, maximum retention, decreasing drop out, improving academic results, target based ranking of districts, ensuring quality education, governance, supportive actions, merit based transfer policy and parameters for ranking of district.

It was concluded that the head teachers of public secondary schools in central Punjab have to face a number of academic problems related to their students. The academic problems related to students were such as: students' health problem, lack of A.V. aids in their classrooms for teaching purposes, students' low enrollment in their schools as compared with the assigned enrollment targets, students' drop out problem caused by due to a number of problems away from school, students' domestic problems indirectly affecting head teachers efficiency, students' attitudinal problems with students and teachers, students' clean and complete uniform on daily basis and students' safety problem.

It was further concluded that head teachers of public secondary schools of central Punjab were facing numerous academic problems related to their schools such as the problem of the availability of teaching and non teaching staff according to requirement, the problem of pure drinking water, the problem of availability of toilets as per students' strength, the problem of functional electricity in classrooms, the problem of number of classrooms as per students' strength and the problem of classroom teaching and non teaching facilities.

It was also concluded that a minority of the head teachers of public secondary schools in central Punjab was facing problems related to quality education of such type as the problem of availability of teaching staff as per student teacher ratio, the problem of availability of teaching staff as per subject, the problem of learning material for the students, the problem of the availability of tab for LND (literacy and numeracy drive) test for class three, the problem of availability of latest version of LND booklets, the problem of availability of teacher guides for lesson planning and the problem of preparation of low-cost, no-cost material.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for the best improvement of efficiency and maximum reduction of the academic problems of the head teachers of the public secondary schools in achieving Chief Ministers' roadmap

The public secondary schools must be provided with infrastructure as per the need and strength of the schools. In infrastructure; classrooms, toilet blocks, boundary walls, pure drinking water points, playgrounds, science labs, computer labs, and electricity connections are of the top priorities. Teaching staff plays a central role in the development and output of educational institutions. So it is recommended that teaching staff should be provided to the public secondary schools at first hand. In case of need, it should be provided urgently from earlier recruited reserve force rather waiting for the upcoming recruitment. Headteacher is considered responsible for each and every problem related to the student. Students' enrollment, students' drop out, students' uniform, students' bag and baggage, students' negative attitude' students' health, students' economic problems, students' social problems, and students' domestic problems are directly or indirectly thrown over the head teachers' efficiency. So it is another recommendation to solve out the problems of the students at government and parental level by the involvement of the community.

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